

Adipocytes time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1833

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1940

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 449

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 543

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 780

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 264

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 2492

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 516

Atrial_Cardiomyocyte time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1132

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 555

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 1309

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 52

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1140

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 1341

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 466

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 930

Endothelial time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 570

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 895

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 648

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 387

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 915

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 626

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 880

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 972

Fibroblast time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 776

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1732

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 102

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 948

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1256

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 802

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 6

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 5

Lymphoid time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 549

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 801

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 630

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 903

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 675

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 292

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 640

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 608

Mesothelial time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 819

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 876

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 790

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 783

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 782

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 844

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 743

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 742

Myeloid time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 748

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 841

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 853

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 724

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 837

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 659

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 907

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 518

Neuronal time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1344

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1023

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 3

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 2

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1501

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 43

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 940

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 755

Pericytes time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1117

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 709

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 662

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 639

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 621

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 630

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 761

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 385

Smooth_muscle_cells time clusters

Ventricular_Cardiomyocyte time clusters

